

Chemically modified hyaluronic acid hydrogels for enhanced bone healing through local metabolite delivery (MetaGEL) (Nr. Izp-2024/1- 0366)

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research project Chemically modified hyaluronic acid hydrogels for enhanced bone healing through local metabolite delivery (MetaGEL) (Nr. Izp-2024/1-0366), 01.01.2025-31.12.2027. Project is led by Ph.D. Kristaps Klavins. The project is implemented in Institute of Biomaterials and Bioengineering, Riga Technical University and Institute of Organic Synthesis. The DMP contains descriptions of datasets related to Work Packages of the Project. The DMP will be updated during the implementation of the Project at least annually.

Summary of the Project: Bone fractures impose a tremendous burden on the healthcare system and economy. Tissue engineering has become a promising strategy for repairing damaged bone tissue. Recently, in this field, the usage of endogenous small molecules – metabolites - has emerged as a novel and powerful approach for regulating various cellular functions, including tissue-specific stem cell differentiation and proliferation. The project aims to develop novel chemically modified hyaluronic acid-based hydrogels to ensure local delivery of cell-function altering metabolites that could be used in tissue engineering to promote bone regeneration.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

MetaGEL

Researchers

Kristaps Klavins (0000-0001-9577-9990)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Chemically modified hyaluronic acid hydrogels for enhanced bone healing through local metabolite delivery (MetaGEL) (Nr. Izp-2024/1-0366)

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Researchers:

Kristaps Klavins (0000-0001-9577-9990)

Organizations:

Riga Technical University

Contact: Klavins Kristaps (kristaps.klavins_3@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

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Grants: [MetaGEL](#)

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-03-31](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

WP 3: In vitro and in vivo evaluation of the developed hydrogels

This dataset will include all relevant data planned for publication under the framework of the Project's Work Package 3. Data within the Work Package 3 will be obtained from microplate readers for cell viability and cytotoxicity assays, flow cytometry for apoptosis analysis, fluorescence and confocal microscopy for live/dead cell imaging and histological analysis, LC-MS, GC-MS, and NMR spectroscopy for metabolomics, UV-Vis spectrophotometry for biochemical quantifications, micro-CT and X-ray imaging for bone regeneration assessment, and SEM/TEM for evaluating foreign body response.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data is being collected in order to confirm the purity of the synthesized materials needed for the creation of the biomaterial embedded microfluidic platform directly associated to the main objective of the Project.

Data origin is from the performed measurements using analytical instruments during the course of the Project's implementation.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, we have considered re-using of any existing data, however in our case it does not apply.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data in this dataset might be useful to other researchers, e.g., material scientists, chemists, chemical engineers, biomedical engineers, biologists, computational chemists and computer modelling experts, as well as industry R&D specialists, and to anyone interested in calcium phosphate and biomaterial physicochemical property characterization and understanding.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata will include measurement parameters of the data included in the dataset described in readme.txt text file.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Due to the potential of Intellectual Property protection data will not be made open, but with a restricted access upon reasonable request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period for data access will be set due to the possibility of creation of Intellectual Property worth protecting via patent application.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is one of the most popular repositories in Europe for any type of data. It is not restricted to specific datasets or fields. Project team already have experience of using it.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

No special tools, generally available software capable of opening data file formats mentioned in 1.1.3.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected data formats are XML, TXT, PDF, CSV, XLS.

These data formats can be open using following softwares:

XML - any text editor,

TXT - any text editor,

PDF - any open source web browser, e.g., Firefox,

CSV - any text editor,

XLS - open-source suite that supports XLS spreadsheets, e.g., Apache OpenOffice Calc.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-06-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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